

¹⁵N studies showed that conventional application of PU resulted in low recovery and that the major portion of applied N appeared to have been lost (data not shown). The plant and total (plant + soil)

recovery of ¹⁵N improved with band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits compared with applying PU.

Band placement of urea solution at 50 kg N/ha in 2 splits is an alternate

fertilizer management strategy for reducing N losses, increasing yield, and obtaining higher NUE to achieve about a 6.5 t/ha yield potential. ■

Transformation of N in soil affected by different sources and methods of N application in a flooded rice ecosystem

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We investigated the effect of applying 60 kg N/ha through various sources and methods on rice cultivar IET4094 during 1992-93 rabi (wet) and 1993 kharif (dry) seasons at the university's farm in Kalyani, West Bengal, India.

Soil was a Haplustalf with a pH of 7.9, 0.85% organic C, 26.32 C mol (p⁺)/kg CEC, and 0.993% total N. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Nitrogen was applied according to the schedule in

the table. We applied 13.34 kg P/ha and 24.89 kg K/ha basally across the entire area at final puddling.

Two to three 25-d-old rice seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing. Various fractions of N in the soil, including ammonium-N, nitrate-N (using 10% NaCl solution as an extractant in the ratio of 1:4, soil:solution), hydrolyzable N (HL-N) (6 N HCl), and nonhydrolyzable-N (NHL-N) (acid-nonhydrolysate) were measured, as well as N losses through ammonia volatilization (trapping evolved NH₃ in 0.1 N H₂SO₄) and leaching (soil solution collected by a piezometer with a porous cup). Rice yield was also recorded.

Applying (NH₄)₂SO₄ basally maintained a higher concentration of ammonium N in the soil than did most treatments during kharif. Soil NO₃-N values

with prilled urea (PU) as a basal application and PU as a split were similar in both seasons while green manure (GM) + PU resulted in a generally lower soil nitrate N concentration. Use of neem-coated urea applied basally maintained relatively high amounts of both HL-N and NHL-N.

The cumulative N loss through ammonia volatilization in GM + PU was similar to that of PU (split) during both seasons. The N loss through leaching was generally lower with the PU as a split than with the other treatments during both seasons (see table).

We concluded that applying PU as a split and GM + PU are the most efficient fertilization forms of those studied. They resulted in generally higher yields with relatively low N losses to volatilization and leaching. ■

Transformation of N in submerged soil in relation to yield of rice cultivar IET4094^a. West Bengal, India. 1992-93.

Treatment	NH ₄ ⁺ - N (mg/kg)		NO ₃ ⁻ - N (mg/kg)		Hydrolyzable-N (mg/kg)		Nonhydrolyzable-N (mg/kg)	
	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi
Control	2.58 d	2.12 d	0.60 c	0.62 d	595.75 d	634.00 d	140.00 d	120.25 e
Prilled urea (basal)	5.34 a	4.27 b	0.89 a	0.89 a	686.25 bc	703.40 b	150.50 c	157.25 d
Prilled urea (1/2 at transplanting + 1/2 at 30 DAT ^b)	4.29 b	3.26 c	0.82 ab	0.89 a	687.50 bc	691.00 bc	164.75 a	168.75 a
Neem-coated urea	3.86 c	3.85 bc	0.88 a	0.68 cd	701.75 a	738.50 a	160.45 ab	165.75 ab
Sulfur-coated urea	3.68 c	3.77 bc	0.81 ab	0.71 bc	691.30 ab	717.25 b	162.50 a	164.25 abc
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	5.71 a	4.99 a	0.88 a	0.78 b	684.50 bc	700.75 bc	156.50 b	160.30 de
Green manure ^c + prilled urea (1:1)	4.50 b	4.42 ab	0.75 b	0.72 bc	673.25 c	681.75 c	165.25 a	163.40 bc

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P=0.05) by DMRT. ^b DAT = days after transplanting. ^c Green manure = *Sesbania rostrata* in kharif and *Anabaena azollae* in rabi.

Effect of substituting sodium for potassium in a lowland double-rice cropping system

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We evaluated the effect of substituting sodium (common salt) for potassium

(muriate of potash) in indica, japonica, and hybrid rices during 1990-91 in three soils with different K-supplying capacities.

Soils (top 0-15 cm) were Yu-yao silty-clay loam (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 6.2, 13.3 g organic C/kg, 1.83 g total N/kg, 19.3 g K/kg, 263 kg available N/ha, 20.50 kg Olsen P/ha, 77 kg exchangeable K/ha, 493 kg nonexchangeable K/ha, and

240.15 kg exchangeable Na/ha; Wen-lin loamy clay (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 5.6, 22.0 g organic C/kg, 270 kg available N/ha, 16.09 kg Olsen P/ha, 219 kg exchangeable K/ha, 614 kg nonexchangeable K/ha, and 319.47 kg exchangeable Na/ha; and Shao-Xing loamy clay (Typic Haplaquept) with pH 5.8, 23.3 g organic C/kg, 719 kg available N/ha, 6.18 kg Olsen P/ha, 137 kg exchangeable K/ha,